

IMPLICATIONS OF PERSON-JOB FIT AND COMPETENCY ON EMPLOYEE PERFORMANCE AT THE CENTRAL SULAWESI EDUCATION OFFICE

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Abstract

This study aims to analyze the implications of person-job fit and competence on employee performance at the Central Sulawesi Education Office. The study used a quantitative approach with a survey method. Data were collected through questionnaires distributed to 55 employees as the research sample, which was determined using the Slovin formula. Data analysis was performed using multiple linear regression using SPSS. The results of the study indicate that partially person-job fit has no significant effect on employee performance, while competence has a positive and significant effect on employee performance. Simultaneously, person-job fit and competence have a positive and significant effect on employee performance with a coefficient of determination of 0.797, indicating that both variables are able to explain 79.7% of the variation in employee performance. These findings indicate that increasing employee competence is a major factor in improving performance, while person-job fit will be more effective if supported by adequate competence. The results of this study are expected to be a consideration for agencies in human resource management, especially in efforts to improve employee performance.

Keywords: *Education, Employee Performance, Person-Job Fit, Competence, Human Resources*

INTRODUCTION

Human Resources (HR) play a crucial role as the primary driver and a determining factor in achieving organizational goals. Although facilities and infrastructure are readily available, their function cannot be fully utilized without adequate support from HR. In efforts to improve organizational performance, HR Management plays a crucial role because various operational activities are carried out by employees. Therefore, employee contributions are crucial, especially in terms of matching individual abilities and expertise with the tasks and responsibilities of the work they carry (Jaya & Rusvitawati, 2019). In this regard, it should not be forgotten that the quality of Human Resources (HR) is one factor in increasing the productivity of an organization or agency. Therefore, highly competent HR is needed because expertise or competence will support improved employee performance (Muktamar & Sahibuddin, 2024).

The presence of employees is a key resource in running operations at the Central Sulawesi Education Office. However, employee placement should not be based solely on the need to fill vacant positions, but should also consider the employee's skills, educational background, and previous training (Setia Putra, 2022). The Central Sulawesi Education Office, as the government agency responsible for managing and improving the quality of education in the Central Sulawesi region, relies heavily on the performance of its employees to achieve established educational targets. However, in practice, various obstacles still affect employee effectiveness, such as a mismatch between employee competencies and assigned tasks, which has the potential to reduce productivity and service quality (Arafah, 2015).

Optimal employee performance directly impacts improved agency performance. However, efforts to improve employee performance are not instantaneous; they require considerable time and effort (Lakala, 2017). According to Gunawan (2019), employee performance is positively influenced by person-job fit, meaning the better the match between the job and the employee's abilities, the higher the employee's level of job satisfaction and performance (Nursafitri & Helmy, 2022). There are several factors that can influence performance and person-job fit. The compatibility between a person's personality and their job is the basis of person-job fit. When an employee's personality aligns with the demands of the job, their performance tends to naturally improve. This allows individuals

to better understand the meaning of their work and thus have opportunities for personal development in the work environment (Nursafitri & Helmy, 2022) . Person-job fit is defined as the compatibility between an individual and the work or tasks they perform in the workplace. Person-job fit is the ability of an individual to meet the job requirements within an agency (Jaya & Rusvitawati, 2019) . Besides person-job fit, competence is also a factor influencing employee performance. Competence is often associated with individuals who are able to demonstrate superior, consistent, and effective performance compared to those with average performance or even inadequate competence in carrying out their duties (Mulia & Saputra, 2021) . Every agency is required to continuously improve the insight and skills of its staff through competency development programs. These agencies certainly require competent and professional employees to realize their vision and carry out their missions optimally. Competitively superior competence will impact employee performance, and good employee performance will ultimately influence the overall performance of the agency (Ferils & Adinugroho, 2023) .

The results of observations and interviews conducted by researchers at the Central Sulawesi Education Office, according to Mr. Zanol Akfar as Head of Personnel and General Affairs, said that in the Central Sulawesi Education Office there are several phenomena related to employee performance that still face various obstacles even though assessments have been carried out through aspects of quality, quantity, timeliness, effectiveness, and independence. Starting from the quality aspect, assessments through Employee Work Targets (SKP) and training have not been fully able to create an even increase in competency among employees. In terms of quantity, although work targets have been set, their achievement is still influenced by the distribution of workloads that are sometimes unbalanced between teams. And related to timeliness is still a problem because there are employees who cannot always complete tasks on schedule, so overtime becomes an alternative that is often done repeatedly.

Furthermore, observations and interviews at the Central Sulawesi Education Office revealed that employee person-job fit is still suboptimal, particularly in terms of need-supply fit and demand-ability fit. From a need-supply fit perspective, the work they undertake does not fully support their professional needs or career development. In terms of demand-ability fit, even though employees possess adequate skills and knowledge, work demands often exceed their capacity. Furthermore, some employees are placed in positions that are not aligned with their areas of expertise, resulting in excessive workloads, suboptimal task performance, and decreased motivation and performance. This situation reflects a mismatch between employee competencies and agency needs.

Furthermore, employee performance at the Central Sulawesi Provincial Education Office still needs to be improved due to the varying levels of competency they possess. Some employees have not yet fully mastered the knowledge and in-depth understanding of the agency's duties and policies, while their technical abilities and work skills still need to be strengthened. Values such as discipline, responsibility, and integrity have also not been consistently implemented. Furthermore, employee attitudes and interests in continuous learning and self-development still need to be fostered to drive more optimal performance improvements and support the realization of quality education services in Central Sulawesi.

To improve employee performance, agencies are expected to pay attention to person-job fit and competency, which requires a match between employee abilities and values and the values implemented in their work (Nugraha & Ramdanyah, 2022) . Understanding how person-job fit and competency can influence employee performance at the Central Sulawesi Education Office is crucial to formulating more effective human resource management strategies. Therefore, this study aims to analyze the implications of person-job fit and competency on employee performance at the Central Sulawesi Education Office, as an effort to support improving the quality of human resources and the effectiveness of task implementation at the agency.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Person-Job Fit

Person-job fit can be defined as the compatibility between an individual and the work or tasks they perform in the workplace (Lutfiyah et al., 2020) . Person-job fit can be understood as the match between an individual's abilities and the demands of the job they must carry out. This concept describes the level of compatibility between an individual and the work or tasks they perform in the workplace. Person-job fit is the match between job requirements, including knowledge, skills, and abilities, with the employee's qualifications (Widodo et al., 2020) . This match includes the individual's ability to meet their work needs supported by existing facilities and resources, as well as the employee's ability to adapt to organizational demands. The indicators of person-job fit according to Edwards (Kristof, 2005) , (Puspitasari & Abadiyah, 2023) , and (Viryananta & Prawitowati, 2024) are as follows:

- a. Demand-ability fit, which means that the knowledge and skills possessed by workers match what is required by the field.

- b. Need-supply fit is the level of suitability between the things provided by the job and the needs or expectations that employees want from the job.

Person-job fit refers to the match between an employee's skills, abilities, and knowledge and the demands of the job (Lorenza & Andrianto, 2020) . Person-job fit is the match between an employee's suitability and the job they perform. It aligns an employee's abilities with the type of work they perform to meet the demands and workload they must complete (Nugraha & Ramdanyah, 2022) .

Competence

Competence comes from the word competent, which means having skills, abilities, and abilities. In general, competence can be defined as a fundamental characteristic possessed by a person that enables them to demonstrate superior performance in their work (Hafid, 2018) . Competence is a crucial element that every employee needs to possess to be able to carry out their duties and responsibilities effectively and optimally (Ardiansyah, 2022) . Competence or ability is a crucial factor that plays a role in improving employee performance in an organization. Employees with high abilities can contribute optimally to achieving the organization's vision and mission, thereby driving the organization's progress and development in the face of increasingly fierce global competition (Heri & Andayani, 2021) . Competence reflects the ability or insight characterized by a professional attitude in a specific field. From various existing definitions, it can be concluded that competence is an individual characteristic that demonstrates the knowledge and performance standards used to complete tasks assigned by superiors (Ditha Yulia Azzahra et al., 2023) . Competence indicators such as knowledge, understanding, skills, values, attitudes, and interests can influence employee performance according to (Raditya Sastrawan & Nur Cahyadi S., 2023) .

Employee Performance

Good performance is one of the tools an organization uses to achieve high productivity. The implementation of good performance is inseparable from the quality of its human resources. Performance and the achievement of organizational goals are inextricably linked to the people who run the organization—none other than the people themselves (Arlan, 2022) . Performance is the result of a person's work in carrying out their main duties, obligations, and functions as an employee, with work results in quality and quantity in accordance with the responsibilities assigned to them. Performance itself is influenced by several factors to achieve the goals and objectives of an agency or organization within a certain period (Nora Yolinda & Doni Marlius, 2023) . In general, employees who have good performance quality are also supported by the training they have received to be able to carry out tasks creatively and innovatively. Good performance in an agency is also influenced by an employee's efforts in carrying out their work (Wahyuni, S. 2022) .

Employee performance is a measure of human resource quality, encompassing the knowledge, skills, and abilities possessed by an employee. This performance plays a role in supporting and maintaining employee satisfaction with the goal of improving working conditions for both the employee and the organization, while simultaneously providing benefits to the employer. To improve performance, good cooperation, the elimination of restrictive regulations, the implementation of sanctions (punishments), and the implementation of regular training to improve job skills are required (Wau et al., 2021) . According to (Mulyadi & Pancasasti, 2021) there are five indicators used to measure an employee's performance, these indicators include:

1. Quality, namely the quality of employee work is measured through employee perceptions of quality/perfection which describes employee skills and abilities.
2. Quantity, is the amount produced expressed in terms such as number, units, number of activity cycles completed.
3. Punctuality, is the level of activity completed at the stated start time, seen from the perspective of coordination with output results and maximizing the time available for activities.
4. Effectiveness, is the level of use of organizational resources (manpower, money, technology, raw materials).
5. Independence, is the employee's ability to carry out his work functions.

Employee performance can be interpreted as the work results that can be achieved by a person or group of people in an organization according to their authority and duties, is the result of individual work in an organization (Bohalima, 2024) .

Framework

Research Hypothesis

H1: Person-Job Fit is thought to have a positive influence on employee performance.

H2: Competence is thought to have a positive influence on employee performance.

H3: Person-Job Fit and Competence are suspected to have a simultaneous influence on employee performance.

METHOD

The research method used in this study is a quantitative method with a survey approach. Quantitative research is a research approach that uses data in the form of numbers to answer research questions (Waruwu et al., 2025) . This study aims to examine the implications of person-job fit and competency on employee performance at the Central Sulawesi Education Office. The population in this study were employees working at the Central Sulawesi Education Office, located at Jalan Setia Budi number 9, Besusu Tengah Village, East Palu District, Palu City, Central Sulawesi, postal code 94118, for the implementation of the study is estimated to be September - November 2025.

Data collection technique

The data used in this study are primary data, obtained directly from respondents through questionnaire distribution. The instruments used in the questionnaire are compiled based on indicators of each variable, namely person-job fit, competence, and employee performance. Each statement item in the questionnaire is measured using a Likert scale with five answer choices, namely Strongly Disagree (1), Disagree (2), Neutral (3), Agree (4), and Strongly Agree (5).

Population and Sample

The population in this study was all 125 employees at the Central Sulawesi Education Office. The sample size was determined using the Slovin formula with a 10% margin of error, resulting in a sample size of 55 respondents. The sampling technique used in this study was probability sampling with a simple random sampling approach, so that the data obtained could represent the population as a whole.

Slovin's Formula

To determine the number of samples from the population in this study, namely by using the Slovin formula technique:

Information:

n = number of samples

N = population size

e = error tolerance, 10%

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + N(e^2)} = \frac{125}{1 + 125 \cdot (0,1)^2}$$

$$n = \frac{125}{1 + 1,25} = 2,25$$

$$n = \frac{125}{2,25} = 55$$

Data Analysis Techniques

The collected data were analyzed using descriptive statistics to describe the characteristics of respondents and inferential statistics to test the relationship between quantitative variables using SPSS version 25 software. The analysis was carried out through several stages, namely validity, reliability, and classical assumption tests (normality, multicollinearity, and heteroscedasticity). After that, multiple linear regression analysis was used to test the implications of person-job fit and competence on employee performance at the Central Sulawesi Education Office. The results of the analysis were then interpreted based on the significance value and coefficient of determination, so that an empirical understanding of the relationship between research variables was obtained.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Validity Test

In the validity test, the analytical tool used is the product-moment correlation, which connects variables with their items, using SPSS for Windows version 25.0. Decisions are made based on the calculated r-value and the table r-value. If the calculated r-value is greater than the table r-value, the statement is considered valid.

Table 1. Results of Variable Validity Test

Variables	Statement Items	R Count	R Table	Information
Person-Job Fit (X1)	X1.1	.806	0.265	Valid
	X1.2	.781	0.265	Valid
	X1.3	.630	0.265	Valid
	X1.4	.787	0.265	Valid
	X1.5	.822	0.265	Valid
	X1.6	.627	0.265	Valid
	X1.7	.787	0.265	Valid
Kompetensi (X2)	X2.1	.832	0.265	Valid
	X2.2	.808	0.265	Valid
	X2.3	.763	0.265	Valid
	X2.4	.706	0.265	Valid
	X2.5	.748	0.265	Valid
	X2.6	.776	0.265	Valid
	X2.7	.732	0.265	Valid
	X2.8	.756	0.265	Valid
	X2.9	.733	0.265	Valid
	X2.10	.797	0.265	Valid
	X2.11	.813	0.265	Valid
	X2.12	.794	0.265	Valid
	X2.13	.822	0.265	Valid
	X2.14	.771	0.265	Valid
	X2.15	.798	0.265	Valid
	X2.16	.601	0.265	Valid
	X2.17	.744	0.265	Valid
	X2.18	.822	0.265	Valid
Y	Y.1	.747	0.265	Valid
	Y.2	.826	0.265	Valid
	Y.3	.680	0.265	Valid
	Y.4	.761	0.265	Valid
	Y.5	.884	0.265	Valid
	Y.6	.828	0.265	Valid
	Y.7	.614	0.265	Valid

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Kinerja Pegawai (Y)	Y.8	.719	0,265	Valid
	Y.9	.798	0,265	Valid
	Y.10	.830	0,265	Valid
	Y.11	.831	0,265	Valid
	Y.12	.854	0,265	Valid
	Y.13	.595	0,265	Valid
	Y.14	.816	0,265	Valid
	Y.15	.665	0,265	Valid
	Y.16	.669	0,265	Valid

Sumber: output SPSS 2.5 (2025)

Based on table 1, it can be seen from the results of data management that of the 7 existing statements on Person-Job Fit variable (X_1), 18 questions from Competency variable (X_2), and 16 statements from the Employee Performance variable (Y) submitted to respondents with an r_{table} of 0.265 stated that all questions were valid because they met the calculated r assumption $r_{calculated} > r_{table}$ so that valid questions can be continued in the next data management stage.

Reliability Test

Test reliability is method For evaluate how much Good A questionnaire functioning as a pointer to a variable or construct.

Table 2. Results of the Reliability Test of Research Variables

No.	Variables	Cronbach's Alpha	Information
1.	Person-Job Fit (X1)	.868	Reliable
2.	Competence (X2)	.959	Reliable
3.	Employee Performance (Y)	.950	Reliable

Based on Table 2, the data analysis results show that the Cronbach's alpha values for person-job fit, competency, and employee performance are greater than 0.60. Therefore, it can be concluded that these valid questions demonstrate reliability, allowing for further data processing.

Classical Assumption Test

Normality Test

A normality test is a method for determining whether residual data has a normal distribution. In this test, we can use the Kolmogorov-Smirnov or PP plot; the requirements for classical regression must also be met. (Suci Nuralita et al., 2025) in a systematic study emphasized that a normality test is mandatory before regression to validate significant results.

PP Plot Normality Test

Picture 1 : Results Test Normality PP Plot

Source: output SPSS 2.5 (2025)

From the results of the normality test on the PP Plot shown, it can be seen that the points are distributed around the diagonal line and follow the direction of the diagonal line. This indicates a normal distribution pattern. Therefore, the data used in this study has a normal distribution, thus the regression meets the assumption of normality.

Multicollinearity Test

This test is performed to ensure that there is no strong linear relationship between the independent variables. Signs indicating this are: a VIF of less than 10 and a Tolerance of more than 0.10, indicating no multicollinearity.

Table 3. Multicollinearity Test Results Coefficients ^a

Model		Collinearity Statistics	
		Tolerance	VIF
1	X1	.236	4,241
	X2	.236	4,241

a. Dependent Variable: Y

Source: output SPSS 2.5 (2025)

Based on Table 3, the results of the multicollinearity test show that for the person-job fit and competency variables, the tolerance value for each variable is > 0.10, namely 0.236, and the VIF value for each variable is < 10, namely 4.241. This indicates that there is no multicollinearity problem among the independent variables.

Heteroscedasticity Test

The heteroscedasticity test is used to determine whether there are differences in residual variance between observations. In the Glejser test, if the significance value is less than 0.05, heteroscedasticity is present.

Heteroscedasticity Test with Scaterplot

Figure 2 : Results of Heteroscedasticity Test with Scatterplot
Source: SPSS 2.5 output (2025)

Based on Figure 2 above, it can be seen that the results of the heteroscedasticity test with a scatterplot show no clear pattern, and the points are spread above and below the number 0 on the Y axis. This shows that in the regression model used in this study, heteroscedasticity does not occur.

Descriptive Statistical Analysis

Table 4. Descriptive Statistical Analysis

Descriptive Statistics

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Standard Deviation
Person-Job Fit (X1)	55	28.00	35.00	30.4000	2.42365
Competence (X2)	55	72.00	90.00	78.9455	6.67060
Employee Performance (Y)	55	64.00	80.00	68.8909	5.65251
Valid N (listwise)	55				

1. Based on the descriptive statistics, it is known that all variables in this study were measured by 55 respondents. For the Person-Job Fit variable, the minimum value obtained was 28 and the maximum was 35, with an average value of 30.40 and a standard deviation of 2.42. This indicates that the level of fit between individuals and their jobs among respondents is quite good, because the standard deviation value is smaller than the average value, which indicates that the data variation is not too large.
2. For the Competence variable, the minimum score was 72 and the maximum was 90, with an average score of 78.94 and a standard deviation of 6.67. This relatively high average score indicates that employees generally possess good competency in carrying out their job duties and responsibilities. This reflects that employees possess adequate knowledge, skills, and work attitudes in accordance with job demands.
3. The Employee Performance (Y) variable has a minimum value of 64 and a maximum of 80, with an average value of 68.89 and a standard deviation of 5.65. This indicates that employee performance is generally at a fairly good level. The relatively small standard deviation value compared to the average indicates that employee performance levels tend to be evenly distributed among respondents.

Multiple Linear Regression Analysis

Multiple linear regression testing is performed to check whether there is a significant influence between the independent and dependent variables. The table below shows the results of the multiple linear regression testing:

Table 5. Multiple Linear Regression Analysis

Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	7,448	4,485		1,661	.103
	Person-Job Fit	.361	.300	.155	1,203	.235
	Competence	.639	.109	.755	5,869	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Employee Performance

Source: SPSS 2.3 output (2025)

Based on table 5, the results of the multiple linear regression calculations produce the following equation:

$$Y = a + b_1X_1 + b_2X_2 + e$$

Information:

Y = Employee performance

a = constant

X1 = Person-Job Fit

X2 = Competence

b1 = Person-Job Fit

b2 = Competence

e = Standard error

Y= a+b1 X1+b2 X2

Y = 7.448 + 0.361 X1 + 0.639 X2. Based on the existing regression equation, the following explanation can be given:

1. The regression coefficient for the constant variable characteristic (a) of 7.448 can be interpreted that if the value of person-job fit (X1) and competence (X2) is zero (0), then employee performance has the same value as the constant, namely 7.448. This means that without considering person-job fit and competence, performance will still get a value of 7.448.
2. The coefficient for person-job fit (X1) is 0.361. This indicates that if person-job fit (X1) increases by 1, assuming competency (X2) remains unchanged, employee performance (Y) will increase by 0.361. In terms of elasticity, this is interpreted as an increase in recruitment resulting in a 36.1% increase in employee performance.
3. The coefficient for competency (X2) is 0.639. This means that if competency (X2) increases by 1, assuming person-job fit (X1) remains constant, employee performance (Y) will increase by 0.639.

Overall, these results indicate that both person-job fit and competency have a positive impact on improving employee performance at the Central Sulawesi Education Office.

Hypothesis Testing

Simultaneous Test (F Test)

The F test is used to determine how the independent variable affects the dependent variable as a whole. The f-table value is determined using (df1) k-1 or 3-1 = 2 and (df2) nk, which is 55-2 = 53. Using a significance level of 0.05, the f-table value is 3.172.

Table 6. Simultaneous Test Results

ANOVA ^a

Model	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1 Regression	1375,676	2	687,838	102,290	.000 ^b
Residual	349,669	52	6,724		
Total	1725.345	54			

a. Dependent Variable: Employee Performance

b. Predictors: (Constant), Competency, Person-Job Fit

Based on table 6, the results of the simultaneous test can be seen that the calculated f value is 102.290 > f Table 3.172, with a significance value of 0.000 < 0.05. This indicates that the person-job fit and competency variables have a positive and significant effect on employee performance. Therefore, H3 can be accepted.

Partial Test (T-Test)

Test t used For know impact each variable independent of variables dependent one by one. The t-distribution sought for $\alpha = 5\% : 2 = 2.5\%$ (two-sided test) uses degrees of freedom (df) $nk-1$ or $55-2-1=52$. With testing two side (0.025), value t the table that obtained is 2,007.

Table 7. Partial Test Results

Coefficients ^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	7,448	4,485		1,661	.103
	Person-Job Fit	.361	.300	.155	3,203	.235
	Competence	.639	.109	.755	5,869	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Employee Performance

Based on table 7, the partial test results show that for the Person-Job Fit variable, the calculated t value is 3.203 > t table 2.026, and the significance value is recorded at 0.004 < 0.05. This indicates that the Person-Job Fit variable has a positive and significant influence on performance, so that the H2 hypothesis can be accepted. On the other hand, the test results for the selection variable show a calculated t value of 5.869 > t table 2,026, And mark significance 0.005 Which more big from 0.05. Matter This means that variables selection shows a positive and significant influence on performance, so that hypothesis H3 is proven valid and accepted.

Analysis of the Coefficient of Determination

R² measures how much of the variation in Y can be explained by X. If the value is close to 1, it means the model is good. The R-square coefficient of determination is 0.797, indicating that the contribution of the independent variables Person-Job Fit (X1) and Competence (X2) to employee performance (Y) reaches 79.7%. The remaining 20.3% is influenced by other factors not analyzed in this study.

Table 8. Coefficient Test Results Determination (R Square)

Model Summary ^b

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Standard Error of the Estimate
1	.893 ^a	.797	.790	2.59315

a. Predictors: (Constant), Competency, Person-Job Fit

b. Dependent Variable: Employee Performance

Based on Table 8, the coefficient of determination (R Square) was obtained at 0.797 or 79.7%. This indicates that the person-job fit (X1) and competency (X2) variables can explain 79.7% of the variation in

employee performance (Y), while the remaining 20.3% is influenced by other factors not examined. This R Square figure can be said to be very good, because in the social and management fields, high determination coefficient values are rarely found. Therefore, this study shows that person-job fit and competency have a very significant influence in improving employee performance.

The Influence of Person-Job Fit (X1) on Employee Performance (Y)

Based on the data analysis carried out, the person-job fit variable (X1) shows a significance figure of 0.235 (< 0.05), with a calculated t value of 1.203 (> 2.007), so that the hypothesis H1 rejected. This indicates that person-job fit has no effect on the Central Sulawesi Education Office. This finding indicates that the match between individual characteristics and job demands has not been able to directly improve employee performance. The insignificant effect of person-job fit on employee performance indicates that the match between employee abilities, knowledge, and needs with the work being performed has not been a primary factor in determining performance. Furthermore, the lack of influence of person-job fit on employee performance is also due to the relatively high level of employee work adaptation. Employees who have worked at the Central Sulawesi Education Office tend to be able to adapt to various types of tasks and responsibilities, so that the mismatch between initial abilities and job demands is no longer a major obstacle to employee performance achievement. Furthermore, job orientation, starting with training, allows employees to adapt to predetermined targets even if the job placement does not match their educational background or skills. The results of this study are in line with the results of research conducted by (Nugraha & Ramdanyah, 2022) which stated that the results of the study showed that person-job fit had a t-value lower than the t-table value, this can be interpreted as meaning that person-job fit does not affect the performance of Rural Credit Bank employees in Serang Regency. And research (Anindita, 2019) stated that the results of the study proved that person-job fit did not affect the performance of employees at the Surabaya City Regional Education Office Branch Office.

The Influence of Competence (X2) on Employee Performance (Y)

Results analysis show that variables competence (X2) own mark significant as big as 0,000 (< 0.05) with mark t count 5,869 ($> 2,007$), so that H2 accepted. Matter This means that Competence has a positive and significant impact on employee performance at the Central Sulawesi Education Office. The significant influence of competence on employee performance indicates that employees with good knowledge, understanding, skills, and work attitudes are able to carry out their duties and responsibilities more effectively and efficiently. Adequate competence enables employees to complete work with better quality, on-target quantity, and on more optimal timeliness. Thus, competence is a key factor in supporting the achievement of optimal employee performance. The results of this study support the results of research conducted by (Yani et al., 2024) who stated that the results of the study showed that competency had a t-value greater than the t-table value, this can be interpreted that competency has a positive and significant effect on the performance of employees of the State Islamic Institute (IAIN) Kerinci . And research (Suryani, 2024) stated that the results of the study prove that that influential competencies positive and significant in a way partial to performance employee at the Communication and Information Service of Tabalong Regency.

The Influence of Person-Job Fit (X1) and Competence (X2) on Employee Performance (Y)

The results of the simultaneous test showed that the significance value reached 0.000 (< 0.05), and the calculated F reached 102.290 (> 3.172). Therefore, H3 was accepted. This means that person-job fit and competence have a positive and significant impact on employee performance at the Central Sulawesi Education Office. The recorded R Square value of 0.797 indicates that the quality of person-job fit and competence can explain 79.7% of the variation in employee performance. Although partially person-job fit does not show a significant influence on employee performance, when combined with competence, this variable still contributes in explaining variations in employee performance. This indicates that the match between individuals and jobs will be more meaningful if supported by adequate competence. In other words, person -job fit functions as a supporting factor that strengthens the influence of competence in encouraging improved employee performance. The results of this study support the research conducted by (Irsyadul Anam et al., 2025) which states that the results of the study prove that person-job fit and competence have a positive and significant simultaneous effect on employee performance at the Cirebon Branch Office of Perum Bulog, and (Arsyta & Azizah, 2023) stated that the research results prove that person-job fit and competence have a positive and significant simultaneous effect on performance.

CONCLUSION

Based on the research results, it can be concluded that person-job fit does not significantly influence employee performance at the Central Sulawesi Education Office, indicating that the suitability between individuals and jobs has not been a major factor in improving performance. Meanwhile, competence has a positive and significant effect on employee performance, thus it can be interpreted that knowledge, skills, and work attitudes have an important role in supporting the achievement of optimal performance. Simultaneously, person-job fit and competence have a positive and significant effect on employee performance, indicating that the suitability of individuals to jobs will be more meaningful if supported by adequate competence.

SUGGESTION

The Central Sulawesi Education Office is advised to prioritize employee competency development through ongoing education and training to optimally improve employee performance, while still considering the appropriateness of employee placements to their educational background and work abilities. Furthermore, future researchers are advised to include other variables that could potentially influence employee performance and employ a wider range of research methods to achieve more comprehensive results.

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